

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GENDER IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The primary notion driving this essay is related to certain linguistic differences between the English and Russian languages regarding the concept of category gender. The essay discusses gender categorization as a linguistic phenomenon and highlights key distinctions between these two languages.

Аннотация: Основное понятие, лежащее в основе этой работы, связано с определенными лингвистическими различиями между английским и русским языками в отношении понятия категории рода. В статье обсуждается гендерная категоризация как лингвистический феномен и подчеркиваются ключевые различия между этими двумя языками.

Modern English's gender grammatical category is very different from Old English's. Many academics contend that English lacks a gender category because of the language's many simplifications.

For instance, B.A. Ilish contends that there is no such thing as a grammatical gender category in the English language. Morphological characteristics cannot identify whether a noun is masculine or feminine. The lexical difference between terms like "actor" and "actress" and "prophet" and "prophetess" is another example.

As a consequence of current linguistic advancements in the area of the system of parts of speech, we were able to change our opinions on how to categorize the gender of modern English thanks to a better knowledge of the nature of the pronominal class of words. For a long time, contemporary linguistics rejected the idea that this category is grammatical, referring to it instead as a semantic category that is always on speakers' thoughts.

Interest in the grammatical category of gender has grown as a result of social changes that began to take place in English-speaking societies in the 1960s and have become more pronounced now. Feminist movements and political correctness movements are two examples of these social movements.

The relevance of the topic is determined by the increasing interest in this linguistic phenomenon due to changes in the discharge characteristic of pronouns and the definition of its main functions (clarifying and substitutive), which are reflected in the noun characteristic.

The problem of determining gender in modern English has its related and long history. The category of the grammatical gender — masculine, feminine, and middle — was inherent in Old English nouns: mona- moon, tigol- brick — feminine, scip-ship, eage - eye - neuter. There were some contradictions with the real gender: wlf-woman, magden- girl were the words of the neuter. The gender category of nouns has finally disappeared in the language of the second half of the 17th century. The masculine is preserved only for males, the feminine - for females, and all concepts and objects, and even animals, are considered to be neuter nouns pronouncing it.

In the English language nouns and pronouns possess the category of the gender . There are three genders in it: masculine, feminine and neuter . For example:

- masculine- father, he , son, boy, king, brother.
- Feminine- she, mother, daughter, girl, queen, sister.

As for the neuter gender, all animate and inanimate nouns are attributed to it ,(subjects, phenomena and animals), which can refer to both female and male (driver, sheep, child, monarch)

It should be noted that some authors distinguish four genders: masculine,feminine, neuter and general. To the general gender in their opinion, are related animate nouns that can refer to both male and female(doctor,baby, horse).

In the Russian language, gender should be taken into account. Gender in grammar may be broken down into four categories: masculine, feminine, neuter, and general.

The study focuses on the fact that the same term might have a different gender in various languages. Turning to Old English, let's look at the term *steorra*, which in Russian denotes the feminine gender. This can be explained by the ways that speakers of various languages think differently. Each word in the Russian language has a specific gender. Since gender is ingrained from birth, it is not difficult for native speakers to define it. The vast majority of those learning Russian as a second language, however, struggle to identify the gender. This is especially true for those in whose native language there is no clearly defined category of the gender. Naturally, a number of questions arise, for example, why the word *glass* is masculine and the word *rainbow* is feminine. This is beyond explanation. But there are criteria by which we define the gender of nouns. Namely:

1. Masculine are nouns:

* denoting males: отец, гражданин, юноша, старец;

*with a basis on a soft consonant, and also on-ш, and on-ж, having endings -а, -я in the genitive singular : конь, пляж.

* the word путь.

2. Feminine are nouns:

* denoting females: внучка, гостья, девушка, ученица;

* with ending -а, -я in the nominative singular: радуга, заря

* with the basis, on a soft consonant and also on-ж and on- ш having ending -и in the genitive singular(the word путь is exception): тень,мышь.

3. Neuter are nouns:

* having ending -о(е) in the Nominative singular : облако , сомнение;

* ending with -мя (ten words): имя, время, племя, знамя, бремя, семя, стремя, темя ,пламя, вымя.

* the word дитя.

There are a number of words (for example, штель(feminine) and тополь(masculine) , whose morphological structure in the nominative case is absolutely the same. In such cases , the alien will need a dictionary.

Consider the nouns of the general gender : недотрога , засоня, невежа. Such nouns give an emotional coloring in the conversational style of speech. The gender of such kind of nouns is determined in accordance to the situation. If we are talking about a male , it is masculine(the same happens to the feminine).

Separately, the essential ones denoting a proffesion or position should be considered : judge, teacher, sculptor. However, they also call female faces because the corresponding forms of the feminine gender are absent. Such as, кассирша(cashier), библиотекарша(librarian), кондукторша(conductor) formed from the masculine gender , are used in the conversational style of speech.

Thus, having considered such a linguistic phenomenon as a gender of noun, we can say with certainty that this grammatical category in Russian has a fairly well-developed system.

Speaking of English, let's reiterate that gender linguistics has an issue with the subject of the grammatical gender of the word. The essential characteristic of the gender as a grammatical category is that the noun must be compatible with other parts of speech that rely on it, such as adjectives, participles, ordinal numerals, pronouns, and verbs in the past tense, like in Russian, for instance. However, it is impossible for an English word lacking morphological gender.

Used literature:

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2. Blokh M.Y.["A course of Theoretical English Grammar"] 2000,383 pages.
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